

A STUDY ON THE CONSUMER PREFERENCE ON LIME BASED AND SLAG BASED CEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the research carried out was to study and understand the different variables that are influencing customers cement buying behaviour, sales and preference. The research includes primary and secondary research. Data collected includes structured interviews, discussion and direct observations. A sample of 361 respondents consisting of few construction companies & builders, retailers, engineers and customers. Statistical tools such as correlation, regression and ANOVA were used. It was found that customers were ready to pay more for the brand that is providing qualitative products. They preferred those types of cement that is having low curing and setting time further they would even will have a change in purchase decision based on the packaging of the cement. Additionally, customers prefer the lime-based cement over slag-based cement. The educational qualification of the customers influenced different variables while choosing the brand. Finally, customers were aware of the pollution caused by cement manufacturing companies and prefer the type of cement that is having less impact on environment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Consistent expansion in the infrastructure and housing sectors have given a new way for the growth of construction industry which eventually benefiting the global cement market. In 2019, over 4.2 billion metric tons of cement was produced across the globe and over 2.2 billion metric tons were produced by China. Cement manufacturers are gaining positive growth in regions such as Latin America, North America and Europe. Despite of huge scope for the growth of construction industry Asia Pacific and Middle East Africa cement industries are facing challenges which is weakening the market growth in these regions. Unfavourable export policies and declining infrastructure spending in the regions are negatively impacting the global cement market. As per the Goldstein Research analyst, the global cement market size is anticipated to reach USD 0.74 trillion by 2024 growing at a CAGR of 8.2% during the period 2016-2024.

The history of the cement industry in India dates back to the 1889 when a Kolkata-based company started manufacturing cement from Argillaceous. But the industry started getting the organized shape in the early 1900s. In 1914, India Cement Company Ltd was established in Porbandar with a capacity of 10,000 tons. The World War I gave the first initial thrust to the cement industry in India and the industry started growing at a fast rate in terms of production, manufacturing units, and installed capacity.

The Indian cement industry is divided into two types of plants; the large plants with a capacity of 400 million tonnes per annum (MTPA) and the mini plants with a capacity less than 2 million tonnes per annum. It is a highly fragmented industry and is mostly dominated by the top 20 cement companies which accounts for almost 70 percent of the total cement produced. Also, if we look at the demand drivers, the housing sector is the major demand driver in the cement industry, followed by infrastructure, commercial and industrial. It accounts for nearly 64% of the total cement produced in a year. Cement is a bulky commodity and cannot be easily transported over long distances making it a regional market place with the nation divided into five regions and each region is characterised by its own demand-supply dynamics. While the southern region is excess in capacity owing to abundant availability of limestone, the western and northern regions are the most lucrative markets on account of higher income levels. Geographically, Andhra Pradesh is the leading state with 40

large cement plants, followed by Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand and Rajasthan having 21, 21 & 20 plants, respectively.

With the rise in the demand and production of cement, there are huge opportunities for the small and medium enterprises in this sector. Government initiatives like AMRUT and smart cities, availability of fly ash, investment in infrastructural development, tie up with overseas players for technological advancements would surely create huge demand for cement surging the growth of the cement industry.

The SMEs in the cement industry face a few challenges too along with the current opportunities. Challenges like limited availability of coal and fly ash, an increase in the clean energy cess, limited supply of wagons, high tax, and fall in exports. Though these threats are not so huge in nature, yet it would impact the growth of the SMEs in the cement industry in the future averaging out their growth rate.

India - world's 2nd largest cement market, both in production and consumption. Supported by high level of activity going on in real estate and high government spending on smart cities and urban infrastructure. Cement production capacity of 502 MTPA as of 2018. Capacity addition of 20 million tonnes per annum (MTPA) is expected in FY19-FY21.

The eastern states of India are likely to be the newer and virgin markets for cement companies and could contribute to their bottom line in future. In the next 10 years, India could become the main exporter of clinker and gray cement to the Middle East, Africa, and other developing nations of the world. Cement plants near the ports, for instance the plants in Gujarat and Visakhapatnam, will have an added advantage for exports and will logistically be well armed to face stiff competition from cement plants in the interior of the country. Due to the increasing demand in various sectors such as housing, commercial construction and industrial construction, cement industry is expected to reach 550-600 Million Tonnes Per Annum (MTPA) by the year 2025. A large number of foreign players are also expected to enter the cement sector, owing to the profit margins and steady demand.

In India, cement was first manufactured in 1904 near Madras since then Indian cement industry has covered a long journey in its growth path. The Indian cement industry has number of fragmented firms. There is lot of new players procuring raw material sources, like limestone reserves on lease basis. Big players are continuously consolidating by acquiring smaller/ mini plant that find it difficult to sustain in a highly competitive price market. The cement market is oligopolistic with more or less homogenous product. In India, there are various cement manufacturers who sell cement and attempt to prove that their product is different and better than the others. The multiple brands available in the market make the brand selection a difficult process. Customer buying process depends on purchasing behaviour and external information sources which influence their buying decision. The project is on the study of purchase behaviour of customers of cement. This paper aims to understand the different variables that are influencing customers cement buying behaviour, sales and preference.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. J.D. Bapat et al., (2007) Since 1947, in India cement was a controlled commodity as the price and distribution was controlled by the government. As there was a gap between demand and supply, Cement industry and the consumers suffered. Thereafter government has reduced its intervention in cement industry as a result availability of cement has increased and there was rapid growth in the cement industry. As the government intervention has been reduced, cement industry improved profitability. The improvement in the technology made the industry to save the energy,

conservation of raw materials and fuels and also utilised the waste generated to improve the sustainability. Indian cement industry has changed its preference from high strength to durable and high-performance concrete.

According to L. Gulbe et al., (2017) The usage of pure aerial lime blunders reduces the water resistance and even the mechanical durability of the material. In order to improve the compatibility,

Portland cement is added to hydraulic and historic mortars. More water is necessary to get consistency in case if the cement content is more. Where the density of the mortar increases and the air in mortar decreases. Mechanical strength of the cement increases with the amount of the cement content in mortar. M. Stefanidou et al., (2005) Lime mortars have been used for centuries in the field of construction. In olden days, the houses and buildings were used to be constructed by using lime mortars which will prove that they were strong and durable although lime mortars were of low strength when compared with the cement mortars. At present they were used for the repair of monuments and for the manufacture of repairs. The structure and behaviour of lime mortar has been influenced by the content and size of the lime mortar.

In the paper by K.V. Schuldyakov et al., (2016) A blast-furnace slag that is used in the production of construction materials and items differ in its composition, dispersion and so on, which leads to the property change of the blended cement. The strength of the blended cement with gradually increasing the percentage of slag will vary in different ways where in a small amount of slag in the cement increases the compressive and flexural strength. Further increase in the percentage of slag will decrease the compressive strength at the early stages of maturing process where as flexural strength remains same. Increase in the percentage of slag in the blended cement will slow down the concrete setting and maturing process. Michael Tate, (2005) There are many properties of cement-lime mortar that are beneficial in masonry mortar application where in the importance of the property depends on the user and the type of application. By changing the cement to lime ratio, the characteristic of cement-lime mortar can be adapted to specific mortar applications. Different users need different cement with the different property as the workability is the important property for the contractor, strength might be the important character for the engineer and durability for the normal household user. Cement-lime mortars have excellent workability with the high flexural bond strength. Cement-lime mortars resist the water penetration through the walls. Cement-lime mortar can increase its strength by adjusting the ratio of cement to lime.

L.R. Manjunatha et al., (2014) The market potential of ready mixed concrete is huge and the perceptions of the customers like builders, contractors and promoters are important for the growth and promotion of the ready mixed concrete. The most consumers of concrete have accepted the ready mixed concrete and the increased usage of the green substitute materials like flyash, has manufactured sand in manufacturing the ready mixed concrete led to reduction of the usage of cement and natural sand. Shagufta Khan et al., (2014) As cement industry is gradually rising with many opportunities and cement is the important component that is used to construct the buildings. In order to resolve the environmental and sustainability issues, companies take several measures and practices to save the environment by considering the financial aspects of the company. These sustainable practices should have to be accounted and reported in a proper format. Companies should report the practices regularly so that the difference between the companies can be done.

Xiaoming Liu et al., (2011) Red mud is a solid waste, is used in the production of alumina and remains as an environmental issue by its disposal. To reduce the environmental effect, red mud has to be utilised in a better way. This utilisation is a large-scale recycling of red mud by utilising red mud in the production of cement. At present only less amount of red mud is used in the cement production due to high transportation cost and alkalinity characteristic of red mud.

According to Mohammed S. Imbabi et al., (2013) There are many challenges, cement industry facing that include scarcity of raw materials, environmental concerns and depleting fossil fuel reserves. Carbon dioxide emitted by the ordinary Portland cement on an average is same or totally roughly 6% of the carbon dioxide emitted by the humans. To produce green, environmentally and economically sustainable cement with high quality, low carbon fuels or novel cement formulations and production methods can be used. Alternative fuels derived from wastes will help in reducing carbon emissions and even reduce energy cost but not all alternative fuels will reduce the carbon dioxide emissions. Martin Schneider, (2015) As the technology is rapidly growing, there were some

improvement in the cement industry that has focussed on sustainable, cost and energy efficient production.

In the paper by H.B.Nagaraj et al., (2014) compressed stabilised earth blocks have manufactured using stabilisers to improve the durability and compressive strength so as to make use of them as strong building

blocks. Strength of the building blocks has been increased when lime along with cement is used when compared with the cement alone is used in the process. energy consumption has reduced by using lime with cement to produce building blocks. Lime as it permits the higher quantities of clay while using will reduce the dependence on natural sand as it is difficult to get. Building blocks can be prepared with in less time by using lime with cement when compared with the time by using cement alone. As the energy consumption is less, there is reduction in the environmental pollution. Further as per Binod Kumar, (2016) Copper slag, a by-product of copper refineries, that is used as a partial replacement of sand in the preparation of pavement quality concrete and dry lean concrete. Dry lean concrete is mixed with the stone dust along with the percentages of copper slag and then mixed with the different ranges of water content to find out the optimum water quantity to achieve maximum density and to improve compressive strength. Increase in the slag and decrease in the stone dust will reduce the drying shrinkage of pavement quality cement. Copper slag usage has not affected the compressive strength at 7 and 28 days. Slag can be mixed with the stone dust as an aggregate before using in the concrete. Copper slag can be used in both pavement quality cement and dry lean cement as a partial replacement of aggregate up to the level of 40%.

Priyanka.A.Jadhav et al., (2013) The partial replacement of the natural sand by manufactured sand has an effect in the compressive strength of cement mortar. 50% of natural sand is replaced by manufactured sand and the compressive strength of the cement mortar with this replacement has increased. Manufactured sand can potentially replace for the natural sand and can maintain the environment as well as economical balance. As natural sand is of high cost and due to the unavailability of natural sand, manufactured sand has been used as an alternative for the natural sand as it has nice finish that result in good cohesive cement mortar.

N.A.Madloul et al., (2011) The sub-sector of cement consumes approximately 12-15% of total industrial energy use.

Among the different sections, grinding consumes 60% of total energy consumption in a cement industry by which significant amount of heat is wasted in grinding as a result improvement have to be made in this section to reduce heat loss. Environmental pollution can be reduced by using alternatives as a substitute for the fuel used in the production process. Emission reduction and energy saving can be done in the raw materials preparation, clinker production, finish grinding, general areas and products by applying different energy saving measures. Therefore, promotion has to be done to create awareness by campaign through media.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The idea behind the research was to study and understand the different variables that are influencing customers cement buying behaviour, sales and preference.

3.1 SCOPE

The study will help the customers to decide on the type of cement that is suitable and the factors that they need to consider while purchasing the cement. The study helps the government in

such a way that the companies need to maintain standards to satisfy the customers need & wants and companies will maintain the standards in their products. Companies will come to know about the customers awareness regarding pollution and companies will implement the sustainability activities for well-being of the society.

3.2 OBJECTIVE

- To understand the different variables that are influencing customers cement buying behaviour.

- To know the factors that are influencing the sales of the cement.
- To know the type of cement that is more preferred by customers.
- To determine the factors that customers prefer while selecting the brand.

3.3 METHODOLOGY

The research includes primary and secondary research. The study consists of exploratory, descriptive and causal approach and depends on both primary and secondary information. Primary data includes structured interviews, discussion and direct observations. A sample of 361 respondents and few construction companies & builders, retailers, engineers and customers were considered. Tools for data collection involved survey through questionnaires. Responses were collected through google forms. The data collection method involved direct interview. A Likert scale 5-point is used in the set of responses for closed-ended questions. In each question, the respondents had to assess in a five-point Likert scale (strongly disagree – strongly agree). Further, the secondary data information was gathered from the accessible sources like research papers, articles and sites such as research gate.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1.1 TABLE SHOWING FACTOR ANALYSIS

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Price of the cement matters while even purchasing in the less quantity?	361	1	5	2.58	.958
If price is more, I will shift to the brand which is selling at my expected price?	361	1	5	3.10	.852
More stock in the factory will decrease the price?	361	1	5	3.42	.860
If the price of the cement is less, I will buy in bulk to save money even if it is not necessary at that time?	361	1	5	2.44	1.156
Brand reputation will allow me to pay even more price for the product?	361	1	5	4.21	1.111
ISI standard mark will be considered while selecting the brand?	361	1	5	4.18	1.159
Quality of the cement will increase the brand reputation?	361	1	5	4.17	1.145
High quality cement will be sold for high prices?	361	1	5	4.15	1.110
Old company is more preferable when compared with the newly established firm?	361	1	5	3.68	.810
Old company is trust worthy?	361	1	5	3.86	.955
Old company will provide discounts for regular customers?	361	1	5	3.66	.825
Low demand will reduce the sales of the product?	361	1	5	3.24	.859

More inventory will lead to more production which in-turn reduce the price because of excess stock?	361	1	5	3.64	.884
Sales will be reduced, if the quality of the product is gradually declining?	361	1	5	4.16	1.087
Presence of the greater number of retailers will increase the sales?	361	1	5	3.99	.962
Retailers will push the products to the customers by positive word of mouth?	361	1	5	3.89	1.078
Early booking will increase the availability of the product?	361	1	5	4.05	1.067
Retailers will be responsible to increase the customer base?	361	1	5	3.98	1.014
Packaging cement will replicate the quality of the cement?	361	1	5	4.16	1.152
Expected life of a building is of minimum 70 years?	361	1	5	4.28	1.066
Slab require highly strengthened cement?	361	1	5	4.07	1.228
Highly strengthened cement will increase the durability of a building?	361	1	5	4.18	1.030
Regular feedbacks from the dealers will let the company know their weakness and can try to improve the strength of the cement?	361	1	5	3.91	1.034
What is the type of cement that you will use while constructing walls?	361	0	3	1.07	.445
High setting time will improve the strength of a building?	361	1	5	2.05	1.311
High curing time will increase the life of a building?	361	1	5	2.57	1.060
I will buy less quantity of cement from retailers to reduce risk?	361	1	5	3.61	.869
I will buy in bulk from company to avail discount?	361	1	5	3.79	1.016
Purchasing of cement in bulk from the company will improve the relations with the company?	361	1	5	3.81	.990
Dealers commission can be saved by directly contacting the company?	361	1	5	3.48	.823
I will prefer to use the type of cement that will not affect the environment?	361	1	5	3.73	1.018
Valid N (listwise)	361				

From the analysis it can be justified that expected life of a building or house is the foremost factor that customers will consider while selecting the cement from a particular brand. In customer view, Good brand will provide cement with high quality meeting all the standards by having ISI mark and this is possible due to brand reputation and goodwill. This makes the brand to charge premium for their quality cement. Quality is one thing that the brand shouldn't compromise at any time and that will increase the durability which in-turn extend the life of a building or house. Packaging even replicate the quality of the cement and customers prefer to use high quality and strengthened cement for slab as it

is the base for construction that holds the ongoing floors of a building or house. Customers were ready to pay more price to brands by looking at brand reputation. ISI standard mark represents the quality of the brand and customers will choose the brand that has standard mark. Quality of the cement is the factor that customers prefer the most while choosing the brand. Customers choose the cement that have more strength and will extend the life of the building. Packaging of the cement replicates the quality of the cement and customer will look at the packaging as that attracts the customer. Above set are predominant factors that influence the customers since cement buying behaviour. So, more focus to be provided on the above variables

4.1.2 TABLE SHOWING RELIABILITY TEST

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.893	34

Cronbach's alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data. As Cronbach's alpha is 0.893 that indicates that the instrument is very much consistent. The respondents have provided consistent response to the items of the concerned constructs. The Cronbach's alpha for thirty-four items or independent variables used to measure the Consumer preference in choosing the Cement brand was 0.893 indicating that the measures have acceptable internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀	There is no impact of the variables like Fineness, Availability, Durability, Price and Brand standards over the consumer cement buying behaviour.
H₁	There is impact of the variables like Fineness, Availability, Durability, Price and Brand standards over the consumer cement buying behaviour.

4.1.3 TABLE SHOWING REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin- Watson
1	.705a	.497	.490	.31144	1.568

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Durability1, price1, Fineness1, Availability1, Brand1
- b. Dependent Variable: Consumer Preference

4.1.4 TABLE SHOWING ANOVA IN REGRESSION

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	34.065	5	6.813	70.244	.000b
	Residual	34.432	355	.097		
	Total	68.497	360			
a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Preference						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Durability1, price1, Fineness1, Availability1, Brand1						

As $R^2 = 0.497$, the model is more accurate and consumer preference will change because of dependent variables. From Anova table we examine null hypothesis, i.e. there is no impact of the independent variables on the dependent variables against the alternate hypothesis. i.e. the variables like Fineness Availability, Durability, Price and Brand standards does not have an impact over the consumer cement buying behaviour.

P-value from the ANOVA table is 0.000 which is lesser than the significance 5% which means we fail to accept the null hypothesis and fail to reject the alternate hypothesis. From this inference it can be concluded that there exists a significant impact of the Fineness, Availability, Durability, Price and Brand standards over the consumer cement buying behaviour.

The adjusted R^2 value is 0.490. This means that the regression analysis can explain 49% of the data. As such, the variables like Fineness, Availability, Durability, Price and Brand standards impact the consumer cement buying behaviour. The P-value 0.000 is lesser than significance value and thus we decline the null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis which in this case is the variables like Fineness, Availability, Durability, Price and Brand standards does have an impact over the consumer cement buying behaviour.

4.1.5 TABLE SHOWING COLLINEARITY TABLE

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	.774	.136		5.673	.000		
Fineness1	.338	.055	.464	6.133	.000	.247	4.045
price1	.389	.039	.414	10.008	.000	.828	1.207
Brand1	.097	.061	.165	1.590	.113	.131	7.645
Avalibility1	.046	.061	.069	.756	.450	.169	5.922
Durability1	-.127	.052	-.256	-2.463	.014	.131	7.631

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Preference

Collinearity table shows that Consumer preference is strongly influenced by fineness that is smoothness of the cement, price of the cement and durability that is expected life time of a building or home because price, fineness and durability are significant. As the VIF values are less than the value 10 , there is no collinearity between the variables that influence the consumer preference.

4.1.6 TABLE SHOWING COLLINEARITY DIAGNOSTICS

Model Dimension	Eigen value	Condition Index	Variance Proportions							
			(Constant)	Finenes1	price1	Brand1	Avalibility1	Durability1		

1	5.935	1.000	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
2	.042	11.837	.07	.00	.18	.01	.00	.03
3	.010	24.296	.88	.00	.64	.00	.01	.00
4	.005	33.859	.04	.98	.05	.02	.03	.11
5	.004	39.759	.00	.00	.14	.03	.92	.33

a. Dependent Variable: Consumer Preference

As the Eigen values are very less, there is no collinearity between the variables that affect the decision or preference of the customer. This means the change in one variable does not have much impact on the other variable on which the consumer prefers while purchasing the cement. The change in variables such as fineness, durability, availability, price and brand standards does not have impact on the other variables in the set.

4.1.7 TABLE SHOWING CORRELATION ANALYSIS

		Fineness1	price1	Brand1	Availability1	Durability1	Consumer Preference
Fineness1	Pearson Correlation	1	.265**	.835**	.826**	.825**	.558**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	361	361	361	361	361	361
price1	Pearson Correlation	.265**	1	.166**	.272**	.114*	.554**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.002	.000	.030	.000
	N	361	361	361	361	361	361
Brand1	Pearson Correlation	.835**	.166**	1	.878**	.913**	.449**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.002		.000	.000	.000
	N	361	361	361	361	361	361
Avalibility1	Pearson Correlation	.826**	.272**	.878**	1	.874**	.487**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	361	361	361	361	361	361
Durability1	Pearson Correlation	.825**	.114*	.913**	.874**	1	.386**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.030	.000	.000		.000

	N	361	361	361	361	361	361
Consumer Preference	Pearson Correlation	.558**	.554**	.449**	.487**	.386**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	361	361	361	361	361	361
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).							

From the correlation analysis it is clear that every variable is correlated with the other variable but there are some variables which are highly correlated. Such as –

- Fineness is highly correlated with brand, durability and availability.
- Consumer preference depends more on price of the cement.
- Brand is highly related with durability, Fineness and availability of the cement.
- Availability is highly correlated with brand, durability.
- Durability is highly related with fineness, brand and availability of the cement

Consumer cement purchase decision depends on the fineness of the cement and even on the price of the cement. Brand reputation helps the brand to gain competitive advantage in terms of availability, Fineness and consumer prefers the branded cement because good brand offers qualitative cement. Consumer purchase decision majorly influenced by the strength variable of the cement that is the durability of the house or building is the predominant factor that the consumers prefer while purchasing the cement.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀	There is no difference between qualification of the respondents on various dimension variables of cement grade selection.
H₁	There is difference between qualification of the respondents on various dimension variables of cement grade selection.

4.1.8 TABLE SHOWING ANOVA

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Fineness1	Between Groups	43.721	4	10.930	45.603	.000
	Within Groups	85.326	356	.240		
	Total	129.047	360			
price1	Between Groups	4.238	4	1.059	5.157	.000
	Within Groups	73.125	356	.205		
	Total	77.362	360			
Brand1	Between Groups	66.283	4	16.571	44.945	.000
	Within Groups	131.253	356	.369		

	Total	197.536	360			
Avalibility1	Between Groups	53.088	4	13.272	45.894	.000
	Within Groups	102.953	356	.289		
	Total	156.041	360			
Durability1	Between Groups	100.179	4	25.045	49.845	.000
	Within Groups	178.875	356	.502		
	Total	279.054	360			
Consumer Preference	Between Groups	10.628	4	2.657	16.345	.000
	Within Groups	57.870	356	.163		
	Total	68.497	360			

P-value from the ANOVA table is 0.000 which is lesser than the significance 5% which means we fail to accept the null hypothesis and fail to reject the alternate hypothesis. From this inference it can be conclude that there is difference between qualification of the respondents on various dimension variables of cement grade selection. Difference in level of education will change the pattern of cement buying behaviour of the customers. Highly educated customers prefer to buy a cement that is having high quality with all specifications needed by them and illiterate prefer the cement that is available at low price. The difference in level of education will impact the customer purchasing pattern in choosing the cement brand.

5 FINDINGS and SUGGESTION

5.1 KEY FINDINGS

- The variables like Fineness, Availability, Durability, Price and Brand standards have significant impact on the consumer cement buying behaviour. As $R^2=0.497$, this means that the regression analysis can explain 49 % of the data & the model is more accurate and consumer preference will change because of dependent variables. As such, the variables like Fineness, Availability, Durability, Price and Brand standards impact the consumer cement buying behaviour.
- 56% of respondents strongly agree to the statement that the selection of cement is very important while doing plastering. People believe that smoothness of cement will be more flexible to do plastering for walls because it can spread easily without uneven levelling of wall.
- Consumer cement purchase decision depends on the fineness of the cement and even on the price of the cement. Brand reputation helps the brand to gain competitive advantage in terms of availability, Fineness and consumer prefers the branded cement because good brand offers qualitative cement. Consumer purchase decision is majorly influenced by the strength variable of the cement that is the durability of the house or building is the predominant factor that the consumers prefer while purchasing the cement.
- P-value from the Anova table is 0.000 which is lesser than the significance 5% which means we fail to accept the null hypothesis and fail to reject the alternate hypothesis. From this inference it can be conclude that there is difference between qualification of the respondents on various dimension variables of cement

grade selection. Difference in level of education will change the pattern of cement buying behaviour of the customers. Highly educated customers prefer to buy a cement that is having high quality with all specifications needed by them and illiterate prefer the cement that is available at low price. The difference in level of education will impact the customer purchasing pattern in choosing the cement brand.

- Cronbach's alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data. As Cronbach's alpha is 0.893 that indicates that the instrument is very much consistent. The respondents have provided consistent response to the items of the concerned constructs. It is clear that the alpha value is 0.893 that is 89.3% confidently can justify that the model is reliable.
- The research is worthy and can be used to draw conclusions that can be used by the company to make the strategies. As the Eigen values are very less, there is no collinearity between the variables that affect the decision or preference of the customer. This means the change in one variable does not have much impact on the other variable on which the consumer prefers while purchasing the cement. The change in variables such as fineness, durability, availability, price and brand standards does not have impact on the other variables in the set.
- 62.6% of people were ready to pay price for the cement that is in the range of Rs. 300-350. People were ready to pay a price that is reasonable and believe that quality cement will not be sold at less price. Customers were ready to pay more price to brands by looking at brand reputation.
- From the analysis it can be justified that expected life of a building or house is the foremost factor that customers will consider while selecting the cement from a particular brand. In customer view, Good brand will provide cement with high quality meeting all the standards by having ISI mark and this is possible due to brand reputation and goodwill. This makes the brand to charge premium for their quality cement. Quality is one thing that the brand shouldn't compromise at any time and that will increase the durability which in-turn extend the life of a building or house. Packaging even replicate the quality of the cement and customers prefer to use high quality and strengthened cement for slab as it is the base for construction that holds the ongoing floors of a building or house.
- Consumer prefer the Lime based cement on slag-based cement because OPC (Lime based) is having less setting and curing time as 62.6% of people disagree to the statement that high curing time will improve the strength of the building or house. Cement that have low curing time will have strength because of the raw material used in the clinker. Curing time cannot decide the strength of the cement. Slag based cement is having more curing and setting time by which customers will not prefer slag-based cement in comparison with the lime-based cement as customers consider even time while constructing the house or building. The time constraint has an impact on the consumer cement purchase behaviour.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS

- From the analysis it can be justified that slag-based cement is used for walls as it is having flexural strength & the expected life of a building or house is the foremost factor that customers will consider while selecting the cement from a particular brand. These similar suggestions were recommended by **K.v.Schuldyakov et al., (2016)** that the slag based cement increase the strength of the building and the concrete setting time. Good brand will provide cement with high quality meeting all the standards by having ISI mark and this is possible due to brand reputation and goodwill. Companies need to provide highly strengthened cement to the customers as the customers were preferring the cement that is extending the life of their building or house.

- From the descriptive analysis it is shown that 57.3% of people were preferring the brand which is eco-friendly & companies need to have CSR activities such as planting trees, saving water etc. These similar suggestions were recommended by **Bidhas Chandra (2014) & P. Kumar Mehta, (2001)** that the pollution and gases released by the cement manufacturing companies need to be reduced to save the environment and this can be done by cement conservation. Therefore, Companies need to have CSR activities to improve the wellbeing of the society and even reduce the pollution.
- From the descriptive analysis it is shown that customers prefer the type of cement that is having low setting and curing time. Customers prefer the lime-based cement over slag-based cement as the lime-based cement is having low setting and curing time. From descriptive analysis it is clear that 56% of respondents strongly agree to the statement that the selection of cement is very important while doing plastering. Respondents believe that smoothness of cement will be more flexible to do plastering for walls because it can spread easily without uneven levelling of wall. The similar suggestions were recommended by **M. Stefanidou et al., (2005)** that lime mortars were influenced by its smoothness and strength. Therefore, Companies need to provide the cement that is having high fineness that is smoothness as it is most preferred by customer.

6 CONCLUSION

- Customers were ready to pay more for the brand that is providing qualitative products with the defined standards i.e., consumers prefer the cement that is of high quality.
- Customers prefer the type of cement that is having low curing and setting time as they believe that the strength of the cement does not depend on the setting & curing time of the cement.
- Customers even will have a change in purchase decision based on the packaging of the cement and the packaging will attract the customers that initiate them to think about the brand.
- Customers prefer the lime-based cement over slag-based cement as the lime-based cement is having low setting and curing time. Customer would like to purchase the of cement that is having high fineness as it is easy to use this type of cement in plastering. So, customers prefer the lime-based cement as it is having high fineness and it makes the customers work easy.
- Customers with different educational qualification have different purchase decisions as different level of educated people choose the different variables while choosing the brand.
- Customers were aware of the pollution caused by cement manufacturing companies and prefer the type of cement that is having less impact on environment.

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